

Edge smooth shunting of a power semiconductor.

Fisenko Aleksey Leonidovich

design engineer PJSC "ELECTROVIPRYAMITEL"

(Saransk, Mordovia, Russia)

fisenkoalexfox@gmail.com,

fisenkoalexfox@mail.ru

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10472140

1) View of the edge (straight or circle) of a thyristor with a shunted cathode (Fig.1)

Fig.1

2) View of the edge of a thyristor with a shunted cathode and with edge shunting (Fig.2)

Fig.2

3) New type edge shunting of a power semiconductor (Fig.3)

Fig.3

The advantage of the new edge shunt is that there are many points on the inclined edge, allowing the capacitive current to diverge from the center of the cathode.

The disadvantage of the new edge bypass is that the apex is at the border.

3) New type edge smooth shunting of a power semiconductor (Fig.4)

Fig.4

The advantage of the New type edge shunting of a power semiconductor of leakage current divergence when the structure is displaced relative to the center of the cathode (Fig.5).

Information sources:

Application Notes for Power Semiconductor Diodes and Thyristors www.proton-electrotex.com